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An Appraisal of the Status of Refugees in Nigeria and France

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ABSTRACT

Wars, hostilities, insurgencies, armed conflicts, homelessness, deprivation, insecurity, abject poverty are terms associated with refugees. This article is an attempt to present some of the challenges associated with individuals who left their homes for safety and protection. It identified insecurity arising from the failure of the government to protect life and properties of the citizens, lack of border protection, and absence of basic amenities for the citizens and governmental irresponsiveness to the plight of refugees as factors responsible for debilitating conditions of refugees in Nigeria. This is in addition to the lack of food, healthcare, shelter and portable drinking water in refugee camps as major challenges to this class of persons. The situation in Nigeria is even made worse when considered in the light of the fact that the government lacks data of persons classified as refugees and casually refer to them as 'internally displaced persons.' In juxtaposing the position in Nigeria and France it attempts to provoke effective governmental responsiveness to meet the plight of this class of persons. This article is of the view that data collation is key to effective planning and protection for refugees in Nigeria. It recommended among others the promulgation of enabling laws modeled after the laws of France and the establishment of necessary administrative bodies to optimally respond to the challenges of refugees whenever they arise.

Keywords: Citizenship, Refugee, Non-Refoulement, Statelessness, Conflicts.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The West African Sub-region in the last two decades has been plagued by inter-state and intra-state conflicts. These conflicts took various forms including ethnic and religious clashes most of which snowballed into full scale wars with dire humanitarian consequences. This position is true whether in Sierra Leone, Cote d'Ivoire, Liberia and in Nigeria. In Nigeria the prevailing pockets of crisis such as those orchestrated by the various sectarian groups, and more recently the case of the unknown gunmen ravaging parts of the South Eastern and the Northern Nigeria had caused citizens to flee their homes and become refugees. These conflicts in the Sub-region are certainly not something to cheer about. This is due to the mind-boggling humanitarian consequences that come with these crises, especially the displacement of people referred to in this article as 'refugees.' Records have it that Nigeria alone accounted for over 2.3 million refugees since 2009 out of this number 1.3 million are orphaned children.¹ In some cases these refugees had to escape from Nigeria to countries less fortunate than Nigeria in terms of social security and are forced to return due to the unaccommodating disposition of those countries. Unlike refugees from the western hemisphere who had to escape to other countries with some form of social security and enormous media coverage, the Nigerian refugees are regrettably not so fortunate as there is almost little or no media attention to their plight. The only attention given to this group of persons is inversely on the perpetrators of the violence on the refugees rather than the victims. This is done by placing focus on terrorist groups such as Boko Haram, ISIS and other localized militia groups by naming these groups as some of the world's deadliest terror groups and their members given amnesty and allegedly recruited into the Nigerian armed forces.² Rather than placing focus on the criminality, devastation of the social and economic destabilization of the actions of these groups especially on refugees and the displaced persons.

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¹H Gao, 'Ten Facts about the Nigerian Refugee Crisis' <<https://borgenproject.org/nigerian-refugee-crisis/>> accessed 30th August, 2022.

²ManurAramide Gombe, Army Graduate, supports 559 Repentant Boko Haram Members <<https://guardian.ng/news/army>> accessed 31 January, 2023.

It is said that it takes more than darkness to hide a thief, thus, it needs to be emphasized that armed conflicts occasioning refugee crises do not just occur, they occur as a lapse in intelligence and where this is the case there is usually a rippling effect on the domestic and international order. Domestically the national economy suffers; the social life of the people is displaced as well as the ecosystem and in the worst case scenario people are hunted and mindlessly killed even in places where they run to for refuge. Internationally, undue pressure is placed on both legal and economic resources including humanitarian aid. The situation is even compounded when the issue is politicized even in the spate of overwhelming insecurity, the major actors cannot be identified or are faceless for purposes of sanctions or regulation to protect displaced persons or refugees to forestall a reoccurrence. The situation is further exacerbated where there is non-availability or access to any form of humanitarian intervention for the affected persons who most often undergo the worst form of dehumanization.

In the case of Nigeria, the absence of an adequate and an efficient legal and institutional framework to alleviate the plight of refugees makes an already bad situation dire. To put it succinctly, here there is no status for refugees whether they are domiciled in Nigeria or seeking refuge outside the shores of the nation. The same position applies to aliens seeking refuge within the shores of Nigeria. The situation is even compounded in view of the fact that there is no database for the documentation of Nigerians outside the shores of Nigeria and Aliens within the shores of Nigeria for purposes of proper identification.

The victims of refugee crisis in Nigeria are people who have been terrorized, tortured, subjected to various forms dehumanizing treatments and conditions including assault, rape and even maiming. These persons are not recognised either as endangered as such requiring special conditions and needs for which the Nigerian state must provide for. Rather they are neglected, exploited and even dehumanized.

Converse to the position in Nigeria, refugees in France are accorded special status in France with special provision made for their welfare and security. This is because the French law guarantees the legal status of persons seeking asylum in France under the Asylum and Immigration Law. The Refugee Status is formally given to persons satisfying conditions defined by the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugee. Technically, one can be given a subsidiary status as long as he/she proves risks of a threat or serious harm to their personal safety once they return to their country of origin. This article therefore juxtaposes the status of refugees in Nigeria and France and proposes a better deal for the welfare of refugees in Nigeria.

2.0 Statement of the Problem

Refugee crises are a global phenomenon especially in crisis prone regions and states. In times of civil or military upheavals especially in armed struggles across the globe there is almost usually the resort to violence, anarchy and use of brute force. The consequential out-come of this state of affairs is that incivility reigns supreme. Under this reign the civilian population undergoes agony and pain. At the risk of being killed they are forced to abandon their homes and livelihoods to seek refuge elsewhere, thereby, becoming refugees and victims of unforeseen circumstances usually for no fault of theirs with no form of security.

3.0 Conceptual Framework

3.1 Citizenship

The concept 'citizenship' pertains to a person who under the constitution and the laws of a particular state as a member of the political community, owing allegiance and being entitled to the enjoyment of some fundamental rights.³ At common law, 'the idea of British subject was rooted in the notion of 'allegiance,' which bond linked man with his feudal lord and in return for this allegiance; a man was entitled to his Lord's protection.'⁴ This accords the individual protection and dominion of a government for the promotion of their general welfare and protection of their individual as well as collective rights.⁵ The most important privilege citizenship confers on an individual is the benefit or protection it confers to the individual to wit security and safety of the person by the state.⁶ This article considers the concept 'citizenship' in the light of the rights and privileges it confers on an individual or groups including social welfare or 'safety net' especially in times of armed conflicts requiring

³K M Mowoe, *Constitutional Law in Nigeria* (Lagos: Malthouse Press Ltd, 2008) 257. ⁴*Ibid*

⁵*Ibid*

⁶H J Laski, *Grammar of Politics* (India: Surjeet Publications, 2004)311, 318 ⁷ B A Garner, *Black's Law Dictionary* (9th edn, USA: West Publishing Co, 2004)1157.

⁸ Slomanson (n...)190.

⁹ *Ibid*

them to support the citizens to move due to displacement. Particularly, it considers the obligation of States to provide some measure of safety nets to their citizens or nationals of other countries in moments of refugee crisis. This threat could exist domestically or internationally.

3.3 Non-Refoulement

The principle of non-refoulement is a concept in international humanitarian law. The concept is a principle of warfare which presupposes the right of a refugee not to be expelled from one state to another, especially in situations where his or her life or liberty would be threatened.⁷ It emphasizes the need for states to treat refugees commodiously in ways that guarantee their safety and welfare especially where they do not desire to return to their places of origin or the place of event causing them to flee for their safety occurred. The principle acknowledges that state treatment of refugees is a problem that overlaps statelessness.⁸ The principle goes to the foundation of the establishment of international law and international humanitarian law which is to maintain the fundamental rights of the individual.⁹ In the opinion of this paper, the principle of non-refoulement urge States to irrespective of their applicable municipal laws treat these class of persons as stateless for the fears or factors that informed the fleeing of their homelands. These may include well-founded fear of persecution for reasons such as race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or holding certain political opinions considered intolerable by the state. It also applies where these classes of persons outside their countries are unable to return to their home countries or their habitual residence or country of nationality, owing to such fears. The same holds sway where such persons are unwilling to return or are able to avail themselves of the protection of their country; then based on the principle of non-refoulement the state the individual runs to for refuge is obliged not to return the individual to his home land.

3.5 Conflict

The term conflict is one of the key terms associated with this paper and is considered to be an intrinsic and inevitable part of human existence.¹⁰ For *Weeks* conflict is a natural part of our daily lives.¹¹ *Frances* viewed conflict as the pursuit of incompatible interests and goals by different groups.¹² He further opined that armed conflict is the resort to the use of force and armed violence in the pursuit of incompatible and particular interest and goals. He identified the worst forms of armed conflict mass killing and genocide against unarmed civilians.¹³ Within the context of this article, conflict presupposes crisis where there is direct confrontation, eruption of violence, free use of weapon and the society witnesses a total breakdown of law and order and essential services completely disrupted. People experience discomfort as a result of lack of food, water and other essential goods¹⁴ and as a result, they have to flee their homes and places of abode to places perceived to be safe and secure thus, becoming refugees.

3.6 Armed Conflict

Shaw did not define but rather choose to describe 'armed conflict' when he said, 'armed conflict exists whenever there is a resort to armed forces between states or protracted armed violence between governmental authorities and organised armed groups or between such groups within the state.'¹⁵ *Conde* also described armed conflict as a 'hostile military engagement between two or more states that may or may not constitute a state of war or a civil war characterized by hostilities between the states and an opposing faction or factions, or between opposing factions.'¹⁶

Conflicts could be international or local. While international conflict is a conflict between two states or more, a non-international armed conflict is a synonym of what used to be described as civil war which is characterized by fighting between the armed forces of a state and dissident or rebel armed forces. It also includes a conflict in which organized groups are fighting one-another.¹⁷ In the past, such conflicts were regarded as internal problems of the state involved, for which international law had no applicable rules.¹⁸ Within the context of this paper, conflicts are considered as armed struggles leading to refugee crisis.

¹⁰W Isard, *Understanding Conflict and the Science of Peace* (Cambridge MA: 1992) 1; S G Best, *Introduction to Peace and Conflict Studies in West Africa* (Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd., 2019), 20. ¹¹D Weeks, *The Eight Essential Steps to Conflict Resolution* (New York: Putnam Tharcher, 1992)ix ¹²S G Best, *Introduction to Peace and Conflict Studies in West Africa* (Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd., 2019)20. ¹³Best (n.17),20.

¹⁴ Ibid

¹⁵M N Shaw, *International Law* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003) 1069 ¹⁶H V Conde, *A Handbook of International Humanitarian Rights Terminology* (2ndedn, University of Nabraska Press, 2004) 18.

¹⁷ Kwede (n...)346

¹⁸ Ibid

3.7 Refugee

Toby referring to the 1951 UN Refugee Convention described a refugee as a civilian person fleeing his country to a foreign country running away from such problems as an oppressive government, religious persecution, suffering or an invading army.¹⁹ In this context he viewed a refugee as displaced persons.²⁰ The inadequacy of the definition provided by the 1951 UN Refugee Convention has led to the making at least three other Protocols all in a bid to formulate a definition that will embrace or encompass all cases of refugee for protection. Amidst this conceptual hiccup, Ladan noted that ‘a cursory consideration of 1951 Convention’s definition and its implication of being covered by it appear undaunted; however, the definitions as to when a person qualifies as a refugee can be problematic.’ It is as a result of this that he noted that States have interpreted this definition and its concomitant provisions in various ways.²¹ While the confusion rages the courts and the academia seem to have been infested by this definitional quagmire. Referring to this apparent challenge Okorie emphasized the limitations to the 1967 Protocol which exercised temporary restrictions on refugee status to those circumstances which had happened as a result of the event occurring before 1st January, 1951 and the geographic restrictions which gave state party to the Convention the option of interpreting this as ‘event occurring in Europe’ or ‘events occurring elsewhere.’²² Woehlcke defined ‘refugees as persons who are living outside their country because of a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion.’²³ He also identified various forms of refugees to include ‘economic refugees’ who are (those fleeing poverty and economic hardship) and ‘environmental refugees’(those fleeing ecological catastrophe) make up the bulk of problems.²⁴ On the part of Surhke the criterion for determining the refugee status according to her is persecution which usually refers to the act of government against an individual.²⁵ This in her opinion excludes those fleeing generalized conditions of violence, insecurity and oppression.²⁶

Contrary to the notion of refugees highlighted above, other forms of refugees have been identified to include asylum seekers, internally displaced persons, and stateless persons.²⁷ Accordingly, the asylum seeker is a refugee who has not been officially recognised by his fled country.²⁸ The process of asylum seeking is usually long and hard, and in many cases this class of people ends up in refugee camps. Internally displaced persons on the other hand were considered to be persons whose homes have been badly damaged by war. This class of people are forced to leave their houses entirely and find themselves forced to find another place within their country to go and settle in.²⁹ The third class of persons coming within the definition of refugees are persons who are stateless.

Another class of persons considered as refugees are persons who are forced to abandon their homes and communities due to the effects of climate change and global warming.³⁰ Yet others recognize types of refugees included in addition to the once listed above migrants.³¹ These are persons outside the territory of their state of which they are nationals or citizens and who has resided in a foreign country for more than one year irrespective of the causes, voluntary or involuntary, and the means, regular or irregular used to migrate.³² According to this concept some migrants leave their country because they want to work study or join family, or leave because of political unrest, gang violence, natural disaster or other serious circumstances.³³

¹⁹ B G Toby, The Legal Framework for the Protection of Refugees in Africa: An Appraisal (2016)(8)(1) *Journal of Jurisprudence and Contemporary Issues*, 195.

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ M Ladan, *Introduction to ECOWAS Community Law and Practice: Integration, Migration, Human Rights, Access to Justice, Peace and Security*, (Zaria, Ahamadu Bello University Press Ltd., 2009), 184. ²² Okorie (n.30), 172.

²³ M Woehlcke, ‘Environmental Refugees’ (1992)(43)(3) *Aussenpolitik* 287-288 ²⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵ A Surhke, In Search of Canaan: A Critical Evaluation of the Causes and Effects of Migration within South Africa, and Strategies to Cope with them’ (1993) (24) *South African Perspectives*, 3-4.

²⁶ *Ibid*

²⁷ Boyan Organization, The Different Types of Refugees <<https://differenttypesofrefugees.bonyan.ngo>> accessed June 27, 2023.

²⁸ *Ibid*

²⁹ *Ibid*

³⁰ National Geographical Society, Environmental Refugees <education.nationalgeographic.org> accessed 27th June, 2023.

³¹ Grace Initiative, Types of Refugees <<https://grace-initiative.org>> accessed 27th June, 2023. ³² *Ibid*

³³ *Ibid*

The definitions of the term 'refugee' in many ways broadened the understanding of what actually is meant by the word 'refugee.' For the purpose of this academic paper however, the concept make reference to person who abandon their homes of habitual residence to seek refuge elsewhere. This is whether they crossed national or international borders for safety and protection.

3.8 Human Rights

The term 'human rights' was first conceptually formulated in the United States Bill of Rights and later developed as a universal concept in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and elaborated in the various international human rights instruments following the United Nations Human Rights Declarations (UNHRD).³⁴ The atrocities and horrors committed by the Nazi regime led by Adolf Hitler of Germany during the Second World War presented the state as the main violator of human rights.³⁵ Irrespective of who violates 'human rights,' the focus here is the understanding of the notion conceptually and rationality for its protection in municipal and international law. For *Maritain*, the dignity of the human person means nothing if it does not signify that the human person has a right to be respected for the very fact of being human.³⁶ Dakas submitted that there are basically two approaches to human rights conception to wit the Traditional Approach and the Socialist Approach.³⁷ Exponents of the traditional approach contend that there is a general scheme of rights that appertain to all mankind irrespective of their nationality, creed or sex. Consequently, Lien, one of the great proponents of this approach observed that human rights are 'universal rights or enabling equalities of human beings ... attaching to the human being wherever he appears, without regard to time, place, colour, sex, parentage or environment.'³⁸

In terms of definition, human rights as known today have no universally accepted definition. According to one source, it is 'a set of moral and legal guidelines that promote and protect the recognition of our values, our identity and ability to ensure an adequate standard of living.'³⁹ Human rights represent demands or claims which individuals or groups make on society, some of which are protected by law and have become part of *ex lata* while others remain aspirations to be attained in the future.⁴⁰

Within the context of this paper, the author is in agreement with *Freeman* that human rights relates '... to ideas of survivability...' ⁴¹ especially to persons considered as refugees who flee their homes and places of abode for safety, protection and perhaps humanitarian intervention.

4.0 Legal Framework for the Protection of Refugees

4.1 National Legal Framework

4.1.1 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999(as amended) The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) incorporated and domesticated certain constitutional provisions for the protection of refugee.⁴² By virtue of the constitutional provision the Nigerian government has ratified some regional and international Conventions dealing with refugees and the rights of other persons affected by wars such as asylum seekers⁴³ thereby according them the force of law at the national level. These instruments provide protection specific to refugees such as ensuring that refugees are not prosecuted for illegal entry or returned to a country where their safety and security would be in jeopardy.

The CFRN 1999 (as amended) also embodied certain human rights instruments for which all persons including refugees and aliens alike are entitled, except where the terms of such provision clearly exclude refugees or non-citizens.⁴⁴ These include the right to freedom of movement, right to dignity of

³⁴ N J Udombana, Human Rights Protection and Good Governance in Nigeria (2011)(2) *Justice Journal*, 37. ³⁵ E Piovesan, 'Socio, Economic and Cultural Rights and Civil and Political Rights (2004) (1) *Sur International Journal of Human Rights*, 21-22.

³⁶ J Maritain, 'The Right of Man and Natural Law' (1943) (trans D Anson) 65. Cited in K A Acheampong, Reforming the Substance of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights: Civil and Political Rights and Socio-Economic Rights (2001) *African Human Rights Law Journal*, 188.

³⁷ C J Dakas, Judicial Review of Legal Framework for Litigation in Nigeria: Novelties and Perplexities <<http://www.nials-nigeria.org>.accessed 18th August, 2015.

³⁸ A J A Lien, Fragment of Thoughts Concerning the Nature and Fulfilment of Human Rights (West Port: Greenwood Press Publishers, 1973) 144-5.

³⁹ Udombana (n.36) 38.

⁴⁰ Eze(n.12) 5.

⁴¹ M D A Freeman, *Lloyd's Introduction to Jurisprudence* (8thedn, London: Thompson Reuters Legal Ltd., 2008) 400.

⁴² CFRN 1999 (as amended), S 12.

⁴³ Organization of African Unity Convention Governing Specific Aspects of Refugees Problems in Africa 1969⁴⁴ CFRN 1999 (as amended), S 34, 38 and 39; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1979, Art. 25.

⁴⁵ NCFR Act 2004, S 3(1).

⁴⁶ *Ibid* S 20 (1).

the human person and others. It also provides that the security, safety, peace and orderly government of the country are the primary responsibility of the government. These provisions one way or the other could be construed as protection for Nigerians from unlawful killings of Nigerians and thus a protection against the problems of refugee crisis.

4.1.2 National Commission for Refugee Act 2004

In Nigeria, the major legal framework for the protection of refugees is the National Commission for Refugees Act (NCRA) 2004. This Act was established in 1989 now under Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004. The Act, aside from defining who is a refugee, went further to establish a Commission for the protection of refugees.⁴⁵ Consistent with the internationally accepted meaning of the term it provides that a person shall be considered a refugee if he falls within the definition of the Act. It provided thus:

a person is considered a refugee, who owing to a well-founded fear of persecution, colonial rule, or foreign occupation, or events seriously disturbing public order, covering a wide variety of man-made conditions which do not permit humans to reside safely in their countries of origin or nationality, and have to seek refuge in Nigeria, including also civil wars or armed conflicts, as well as due to the conditions of famine and natural catastrophes.⁴⁶

Under the Act however, a person shall not be considered to be a refugee in the following circumstances:

- a) When there are serious reasons to believe that he or she has committed a crime against humanity, as defined in any international instrument to which Nigeria is a party and which has been drawn up to make provisions in respect of such crimes; or he has committed a serious non-political crime outside Nigeria prior to his entry;
- b) He has been guilty of acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the Organisation of African Unity.⁴⁷

The foregoing provisions of the National Commission for Refugees Act (NCRA) 2004 are most instructive to this article as it provided a statutory definition of the concept 'refugee' within Nigeria. The NCRA 2004 specifically stated that aside from wars and armed conflicts famine and other natural disasters are factors affecting the individual for which he or she could be considered as a refugee. Within the context of the extant Act fugitives or other persons who are on the run do not qualify as refugees and thus cannot be accepted into Nigeria. But, the National Commission for Refugees Act (NCRA) 2004 cannot within the context of this article be considered a holistic legal framework owing to its inability to address the gray areas of this article especially on the 'status of refugees' in Nigeria. For not providing any such status it is considered as deficient in scope which makes this paper most desirable.

4.1.3 Criminal Code Act 2004

In Nigeria there are two main legal frameworks regulating criminal conducts namely the Criminal Code Act 2004 and the Penal Code Act 2004. The Criminal Code Act operates in the Southern parts of Nigeria, while its counterpart in the Northern parts is the Penal Code Act 2004. For purposes of this paper the provisions of the both Codes shall be discussed

together. The Nigeria Criminal Code Act embodies provisions prohibiting certain acts done during armed conflicts and provides appropriate liabilities and punishments for those acts or omissions prohibited as crimes. Although these Acts or Omissions are not styled 'war crimes' under the Code, what is material is that such acts or omissions are prohibited as crimes and punishable thereunder regardless of the circumstances they were perpetrated. The relevant consideration however is whether they constitute elements of the alleged offence and once the constitutive elements are established the offender or culprits are held criminally liable and appropriate penalties meted out.

Under the Criminal Code Act and the Penal Codes, it is criminal to intentionally take the life of another person. Thus, where there are intentional killings or taking of life in armed conflicts whether or not the person is a refugee the offender is held responsible for murder or culpable homicide punishable with death.⁴⁸ The punishment for such killings upon conviction is death depending upon the mitigating circumstances. This is exclusive of the circumstances where the taking of life is

⁴⁷ NCFR Act 2004, S 20(2) of and OAU Convention Art. 5(c).

⁴⁸ Criminal Code Act 2004, S 316; Penal Code Act 2004, S 221.

⁴⁹ CFRN 1999 (as amended), S 33(2)(a)-(c).

exonerated under the Constitution of the Federal Republic⁴⁹ all other death caused otherwise than by

such constitutional exceptions amounts to unlawful homicide for which the offender is held gravely responsible. Indeed, where death has been caused by an act not intended to cause the same, the offender may still not be absorbed of responsibility; the only effect of the absence of the intention to kill will lead to a mitigation of punishment. In that circumstance the offender may be responsible for the lesser offence of manslaughter or culpable homicide not punishable with death.⁵⁰ By these provisions, any form of massacre, attacks on civilians or internally displaced persons, those responsible for the killings could be prosecuted under these two laws. Aside from murder or homicide punishable with death, other atrocities committed either by state actors, security operatives and other armed militias in internal clashes which are penalised by the Codes include grievous bodily hurt, assault, rape and others.⁵¹

4.1.4 Armed Forces Act 2004

Unlike the Criminal Code Act 2004 and Penal Code Act 2004 the Armed Forces Act 2004 applies only to persons who are subject to service laws.⁵² It is noteworthy that most of the crimes already considered above are equally penalised under the Armed Forces Act when committed by those it applies to. Examples of these are acts of murder, extortion and other forms of ill treatment of civilians.⁵³ In the circumstance men of the armed forces who commit either of the enumerated atrocities under the Armed Forces Act during internal armed conflicts can be arraigned by the military authorities in a court martial. Where the officer or officers are convicted for the acts alleged the offenders shall be liable for imprisonment or other appropriate for terms as specified by the enabling Act. Where the offence is an assault, the punishment is terms not less than two years.⁵⁴ Where the assault results in grievous bodily harm through the use of dangerous weapons, the penalty shall be a term not exceeding seven years; the offence of murder attracts a death penalty.⁵⁵

By virtue of the above provisions, it behooves combating military personnel to operate within the rules of engagement to ensure protection to victims of armed conflicts; particularly humanity as any act of torture or hostility against civilians in whatever guise be it refugees or internally displaced persons are fully and very well protected.

4.1.5 Cyber Crimes (Prohibition and Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015

The Cyber Crime (Prohibition and Prevent ETC.) Act, 2015 is another piece of legislative framework providing for the protection of civilians against acts capable of causing violence and prosecution of certain offences committed in Nigeria using cyberspace. It also ensured the security of citizens and advances online security and the protection of the use of electronic systems, networks, electronic communications, data and computer programs, rights of citizens.⁵⁶ The Act is considered to be instrumental for the regulation and enforcement of hate messages capable of causing wanton killings and as well-made provisions for the punishment and deterrence of possible offenders who commits hate crimes capable of causing refugee crisis. Specifically, Section 26 of the Act makes provisions for racist and xenophobic offences. It disallowed the distribution or production of racist or xenophobic material to the public through a computer system or network.⁵⁷ Also prohibited by the EA is the issuance of threats through a computer system or network to other persons for belonging to a group distinguished by race, colour, decent national or ethnic origin, as well as, religion if used as a pretext for any of these factors.⁵⁸

Still within the provisions of the Act, it is prohibited for any person to insult others publicly whether through the use of a computer system or network. Where the reasons for the insult is as a result of a group identified or distinguished by race, colour, descent, or national or ethnic origin, as well as religion then the person is guilty of an offence and liable on conviction to imprisonment for a term of not more than five (5) years or to a fine not more than ₦10,000.000.00 or both fine and imprisonment.⁵⁹

⁵⁰Penal Code Act,2004, Ss 224 and 275; Criminal Code Act 2004.

⁵¹Criminal Code Act, 2004, Ss 330 and 338; also, Penal Code Act 2004, S240.

⁵²Armed Forces Act, 2004, S 130.

⁵³*Ibid* Ss 104,105, 106,107,108, 109, 110, 111, and 113.

⁵⁴*Ibid* 104 (d).

⁵⁵*Ibid* 104(2)(a) and (b).

⁵⁶ Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015, Explanatory Memorandum ii. ⁵⁷ *Ibid*,s.26(1) (a).

⁵⁸ *Ibid* (b).

⁵⁹ *Ibid*,s.26(1)(c)(iii).

Section 26(2) of the Act defined the term ‘crime against humanity’ to include any of the following

acts committed as part of widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population, with knowledge of the attack: murders, extermination, enslavement, deportation, or forcible transfer of population, imprisonment, torture, rape, sexual slavery, forced prostitution, forced pregnancy, enforced sterilization, or any other form of sexual violence of comparable gravity, persecution against an identifiable group on political, racial, national, ethnic, cultural, religious or gender grounds, enforced disappearance of persons, the crime of apartheid, other inhuman acts of similar character intentionally causing grave suffering or serious bodily or mental injury.⁶⁰

Under the provisions of the Act, 'racist or xenophobic material' refers to written or printed material, any other image or any other representation of ideas or theories, which advocates, promotes or incites hatred, discrimination or violence, against any individual group of individuals, based on race, colour, descent or national or ethnic origin, as well as religion if used as a pretext for any of these factors.⁶¹ This legislation in the opinion of this thesis serves only a limited purpose considering the scope of offences it is meant to provide for which are offences committed through the use of computers or in the cyberspace. The limited nature of the Cyber Security Act notwithstanding, it is relevant and considered useful in the protection of the civilian population in Nigeria against acts capable of causing or instigating refugee crises.

4.1.6 Terrorism Prevention (Amendment) Act, 2011

The Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011 defines an Act to be a terrorist act where it is deliberately done with malice aforethought and which may seriously harm or damage the country or an international organisation.⁶² Under this Act an act also constitutes or amounts to terrorism when it is done deliberately with malice aforethought and is intended or can reasonably be regarded as having been intended to unduly compel a government or international organisation to perform or abstain from performing any act.⁶³ By virtue of the Act, a terrorist act is committed when, done with the requisite intent, it seriously intimidates a population,⁶⁴ or seriously destabilizes or destroys the fundamental political organisation.⁶⁵

It is also a terrorist act to influence a government or international organization by intimidation or coercion.⁶⁶ In the same vein it also amounts to a terrorist act where it involves or causes an attack upon a person's life that possibly results in serious bodily harm or death.⁶⁷ Furthermore, intimidating or coercing a government or international organisation also constitutes a terrorist act where it involves or causes: the kidnapping of a person, or destruction of a government or public facility, or private property, among others. This also applies where the acts are likely to endanger human life or result in major economic loss.⁶⁸

Also in addition to the statutory definition of terrorism is the omnibus provision that captures any act or omission within or outside Nigeria which constitutes an offence within the scope of any counter-terrorism treaty duty ratified by Nigeria.⁶⁹ Nevertheless, strikes and demonstrations are excluded from the statutory definition of terrorist acts, provided they are not to seriously intimidate a population or influence a government or international organization by coercion or intimidation.⁷⁰ Under the Act acts of terrorism include 'an act which constitutes an offence under the various agreements and conventions ratified by Nigeria.'⁷¹

In the opinion of this paper, the provisions of the instant Act is instructive in tackling the menace of terrorism in Nigeria which as already noted accounts for many of the cases of displacements, including internally displaced persons and refugees in Nigeria. To this end, this paper finds the Terrorism Prevention (Amendment) Act 2011 as one legal framework that impinges on the subject of this article.

⁶⁰ Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc) Act, 2015, Explanatory Memorandum ii. ⁶¹ *Ibid*, s 26 (2).

⁶² Terrorism Prevention (Amendment) Act, 2011, S 1(2)(a)

⁶³ *Ibid* S 1(2)(b)(i)

⁶⁴ *Ibid* 1(2)(b)(ii)

⁶⁵ *Ibid* 1(2)(b)(iii)

⁶⁶ *Ibid* 1 (2)(iv)

⁶⁷ *Ibid* 1 (2)(c)(i)

⁶⁸ *Ibid* 1(2)(c)(ii)-(iii)

⁶⁹ *Ibid* 1(2)(d)

⁷⁰ *Ibid* 1(3)

⁷¹ *Ibid* S 19 (g)

5.0 Institutional Framework

5.1 National Institutional Frameworks for the Protection of Refugees 7.1.1 National Commission for Refugees

The main institutional framework for the protection of refugees in Nigeria is the National Commission for Refugees (NCR). This Commission was established in 1989 and codified under the laws of the federation of Nigeria 1990 but now under the National Commission for Refugees, etc. Act Cap N21 Laws of the Federation 2004. The Commission was created with a view to protecting and safeguarding the interests of refugees in Nigeria. The Commission operates under the supervision of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation (SGF). The Commission shall be constituted by a Chairman, vice chairman, a representative of the SGF, Commissioner for refugees, Permanent Secretary to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs all appointed by the President. Others are a representative of the Secretary to the Federal Government as Vice Chairman, the Federal Commissioner for Refugees or his representative, the Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs or his representative and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees in Nigeria as observer.⁷²

Under the Act the term refugee is defined as thus:

...a person is considered a refugee, who owing to a well-founded fear of persecution, colonial rule, or foreign occupation, or events seriously disturbing public order, covering a wide variety of man made conditions which do not permit humans to reside safely in their countries of origin or nationality, and have to seek refuge in Nigeria, including also civil wars or armed conflicts, as well as due to the conditions of famine and natural catastrophes.⁷³

Under the following circumstances however, a person shall not be considered or granted a refugee status these include in Nigeria where there are serious reasons to believe that he or she has committed a crime against humanity. This is as defined in any international instrument to which Nigeria is a signatory and which has been drawn up to make provisions in respect of such crimes or he has committed a serious non-political crime outside Nigeria prior to his entry. A person applying for a refugee status in Nigeria shall also not be considered where he has been guilty of acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the Organisation of African Unity.⁷⁴ The applicant and every member of his family shall be allowed to remain in the country pending the decisions of the Board.⁷⁵

Where the application is rejected, the applicant shall be given reasonable time to seek admission as a refugee into another country. Whoever, where the application for refugee status is granted, the applicant and his family shall be issued with an identity card in the form prescribed by the Minister of internal affairs. They shall also be issued with a residence permit and shall be subjected to all laws in force within Nigeria.⁷⁶ In accordance with Article 28 of the 1951 Convention and Article VI of the OAU Convention the applicant and his family shall be issued with the United Nations Travel Document.

5.1.2 National Emergency Management Agency

The National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) is yet another key institutional framework set up by law to respond to certain national emergencies.⁷⁷ The agency is mainly responsible to coordinate responses to disasters in Nigeria. From its inception this agency has been in the forefront of tackling all forms of disaster including environmental or natural disasters and manmade disasters. Such as natural or environmental disasters the agency has been responsible for include floods, landslides and the challenges of internally displaced persons from ethnic and religious violence and so on and so forth. NEMA has also undertaken the resettlement of IDPs and other Nigerian returnees from Cameroon. It mainly performs its duties by providing food, temporary shelters, and clothing to this class of people.⁷⁸ The core areas of expertise of the agency include training, search and rescue, finance and administration, relief and rehabilitation. In performing its duties NEMA collaborates with the Federal Road Safety Commission, Federal Fire Service, Nigerian Security and Civil Defence and the Nigerian Red Cross Society.⁷⁹

⁷² National Commission for Refugees Act 2004, S 3(1)14.

⁷³ *Ibid.*, S 20(1).

⁷⁴ *Ibid.*

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

⁷⁶ National Commission for Refugees Act 2004, S 20(1).

⁷⁷ NEMA Act 1999,

⁷⁸ The National Emergency Management Agency <http://www.nema.gov.ng/index.htm> accessed 1st January, 2023.

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*

5.2 International Institutional Frameworks

5.2.1 France Refugee Council

French Refugee Council (FRC) is an independent humanitarian and non-governmental organization founded by volunteers in 2013 in response to the refugee crisis in Europe under the UN Convention for Refugees and to ensure refugees are able to find safety and protection. Since its establishment, FRC has sought to provide practical support to asylum seekers and refugees and has been supporting refugees to re-build their lives, with an ultimate goal that all refugees have a decent life as a full member of the society, self-determined and recognized as human beings with skills, experiences, ideas and thoughts. FRC as a refugee lead organization speaks up for asylum seekers and refugees by ensuring that they have access to education, employment opportunities, legal information and can make economic contributions to their host communities.⁸⁰

FRC with its vast network of volunteers directly work with the asylum seekers and refugees to ensure they have a stronger and more influential voice and can contribute with their expertise to smoothen their integration in their host communities. FRC is working towards creating a basis for refugees to share their knowledge and experience and advocates for their inclusion both at the national and European level. FRC is supported by a dedicated team of 480 volunteers all over France by offering practical support and advice to asylum seekers and refugees throughout their journey in France and offer a helping hand to support and empower them to rebuild their lives.⁸¹

5.2.2 Migration Policy Institute

The Migration Policy Institute is a nonpartisan body which seeks to improve immigration and integration policies through authoritative research and analysis, opportunities for learning and dialogue and the development of new ideas to address complex policy questions.⁸² Founded in 2001, the Migration Policy Institute (MPI) has thus far established itself as a leading institution in the field of migration policy and as a source of authoritative research, learning opportunities, and new policy ideas.⁸³

MPI maintains a special committee that works on immigration and integration policies in North America and Europe, where its two offices are located and it is also active around the world as it adopts a global and comparative approach to migration issues when possible. The institute is guided by the belief that countries need to have sensible and well thought-out immigration and integration policies in order to ensure the best outcomes for both immigrants and receiving communities.⁸⁴

The institute provides access and timely data, information and analysis on immigration and integration issues that cover the major issues on which policymakers and the general public need information. It also pursues research that fills major gaps of understanding around migration flows and immigration and integration policy. Additionally, it assesses the effectiveness of current migration and integration policies, as well as the impact of migration on labour markets, educational outcomes, and social cohesion.⁸⁵

The institute also promotes a trusted space for dialogue and a series of learning opportunities around ways to address immigration and integration issues. This it does by providing technical assistance to policymakers, practitioners and nongovernmental organisations that are trying to solve specific immigration and integration challenges. It also develops innovative policy ideas to address immigration and integration challenges more effectively.⁸⁶

MPI is structurally organised into three major programme areas to wit, the United States Immigration Policy Programme, the National Center on Immigrant Intention Policy and the International Programme on migration policy. It further has a number of initiatives including the Latin America and Caribbean Initiative and Transatlantic Council on Migration. Its sister organization, MPI Europe, located in Brussels, provides fresh thought, authoritative data and global analysis on international migration and refugee trends. It also offers a series of interactive data tools, maps, and other resources via its user-friendly Migration Data Hub.

⁸⁰ France Refugee Council, <https://frenchrefugeecouncil.com/> accessed 30th of September, 2022. ⁸¹ France Refugee Council, <https://frenchrefugeecouncil.com/> accessed 30th of September, 2022. *ibid*

⁸² M Mittelstadt, About Migration Policy <<https://www.migrationpolicy.org/>> accessed 7th June 2023. ⁸³ *Ibid*

⁸⁴ *Ibid*

⁸⁵ *Ibid*

⁸⁶ *Ibid*

6.0 The status of refugees in Nigerian

The Nigerian law does not provide any special status for refugees or internally displaced persons. However, it could be argued that the CFRN 1999 (as amended) which is the grund norm embodies provisions requiring the National assembly to ratify conventions and treaties entered into by the executive before such treaties can have the force of law in Nigeria.⁸⁷ By virtue of the constitutional provision, however, the Nigerian government has ratified some regional and international Conventions dealing with refugees and the rights of other persons affected by wars such as asylum seekers. These include the Organization of African Unity Convention Governing Specific Aspects of Refugees Problems in Africa 1969; thereby giving it equal force of law at the national level. These instruments provide protection specific to refugees such as ensuring that refugees are not prosecuted for illegal entry or returned to a country where their safety and security could be in jeopardy.

The CFRN 1999 (as amended) also embodied certain human rights instruments for which all persons including refugees and aliens alike are entitled, except where the terms of such provision clearly exclude refugees or non-citizens.⁸⁸ These include the right to freedom of movement, right to dignity of the human person and others. It also provides that the security, safety, peace and orderly government of the country are the primary responsibility of the government. These provisions one way or the other could be construed as protection for Nigerians and refugees from unlawful killings of Nigerians and thus a protection against the problems of refugee crisis. Aside from the above cited municipal, regional and above international legal instruments for which Nigeria is a signatory to, there is no instrument in Nigeria as it may be said which affords special status domestically for refugees or internally displaced persons and in Nigeria.

6.1 The Status of Refugees in France

Unlike Nigeria, the constitution of France specially provides a legal status for refugees and those seeking asylum generally in France. The guarantee is provided under the Asylum and Immigration Law of France. Under the law there are generally two types of asylum protections classified by the French asylum law: Refugee status and Subsidiary status. The Refugee status formally would be given to persons satisfying conditions which are defined by Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees of UNHCR. Meanwhile, the subsidiary status could be possibly given to any other type of asylum seekers who do not meet the criteria of refugee status recognition. Generally, one can be given a subsidiary status as long as he/she proves risks of a threat or serious harm to their personal safety once they return to their origin country.⁸⁹

Besides, any of the following situations mentioned by the asylum law could lead to the denial of applications:

- (a) An overt threat could be seen and proven if the applicant wishes to enter French territory;
- (b) A previous sentence or punishment for terrorism had been imposed on the applicant, which would be regarded as a serious harm to the French society.⁹⁰

Other than the legal residency in France, asylum seekers could also apply for French Citizenship as other immigrants. Usually, a five-year of dwelling in France territory would be required before the application, for asylum seekers who get a refugee status, that period could

be exempted and they could apply for the naturalisation at once if they wish. However, asylum seekers who get a subsidiary status must still obey the normal rule and no exemptions applied.⁹¹

Support on personal finance and housing would also become available since the asylum seeker starts his or her application procedure. Normally, if the asylum seeker found himself under a specific level which observed by the government, a minimum financial assist equals to €6.80 per day would be given to the asylum seeker at the end of the month (Lump sum).⁹²

⁸⁷CFRN 1999 (as amended), S 12.

⁸⁸CFRN 1999 (as amended), S 34, 38 and 39; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1979, Art. 25.

⁸⁹Refugees, United Nations High Commissioner for. "Refugee status, subsidiary protection, and the right to be granted asylum under EC law, María-Teresa Gil-Bazo"UNHCR.

<<https://www.unhcr.org/search/working/45993882/>> Accessed 19th May 2019.

⁹⁰N Boring, "Refugee Law and Policy: France". <<https://www.loc.gov/law/help/refugee-law/france.hph>> Accessed 18th May, 2018

⁹¹Ibid.

⁹²Ibid.

The number of money support could be changed according to the different family populations of asylum seekers. On housing, asylum seekers could temporarily live in the rooms provided by CADA (Centres for the Reception of Asylum Seekers), which could last for six months before the asylum seeker finished finding his or her own place to live.⁹³

Given the above it can validly be said that unlike the Nigerian counterpart the constitution of France entrenched special status and recognition to individuals and persons seeking asylum or refugee status to them.

6.2 Analysis Between the Positions in Nigeria and France In spite of the fact that the situation in the both jurisdictions are quite different due to the fact that as noted in Nigeria there are actually no municipal laws in this area which implies that the Nigerian law does not protect refugees. But in the case of France, as said earlier the basic law protects refugees and asylum seekers. It therefore provides for and protects this class of people irrespective of the circumstance confronting them. Nevertheless, there are certain similarities in the both jurisdictions which this thesis considers imperative to bring to fore. For example, the both countries are signatories of major international instruments recognised as treaties and conventions that provide for basic standards of living for refugees and provisions to be made for their safety and those of their dependents. The basis of which France has from time to time modified its laws to adequately protect refugees, but the same cannot be said of Nigeria. This is because of the fact that Nigeria is a signatory of these international legal frameworks for the protection of refugees, it has not significantly taken measures to stratify or provide any form of status in Nigeria.

6.4 Dissimilarities between the situation in Nigeria and France

Although Nigeria has passed certain laws relating to refugees including the National Commission for Refugees Act (NCRA) 2004, This Act was established in 1989 now under Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004. The Act, aside from defining who is a refugee, went further to establish a Commission for the protection of refugees.⁹⁴ Consistent with the internationally accepted meaning of the term it provides that a person shall be considered a refugee if he falls within the definition of the Act. It provided thus:

a person is considered a refugee, who owing to a well-founded fear of persecution, colonial rule, or foreign occupation, or events seriously disturbing public order, covering a wide variety of man-made conditions which do not permit humans to reside safely in their countries of origin or nationality, and have to seek refuge in Nigeria, including also civil wars or armed conflicts, as well as due to the conditions of famine and natural catastrophes.⁹⁵

Under the Act however, a person shall not be considered to be a refugee in the following circumstances:

- a) When there are serious reasons to believe that he or she has committed a crime against humanity, as defined in any international instrument to which Nigeria is a party and which has been drawn up to make provisions in respect of such crimes; or he has committed a serious non-political crime outside Nigeria prior to his entry;
- b) He has been guilty of acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the Organisation of African Unity.⁹⁶

It is submitted that the foregoing provisions of the National Commission for Refugees Act (NCRA) 2004 are most instructive to this thesis as it provided a statutory definition of the concept of who exactly is a refugee within Nigeria. The NCRA 2004 specifically stated that aside from wars and armed conflicts famine and other natural disasters are factors affecting the individual for which he or she could be considered as a refugee. Within the context of the extant Act fugitives or other persons who are on the run do not qualify as refugees and thus cannot be accepted into Nigeria. But, the National Commission for Refugees Act (NCRA) 2004 cannot within the context of this thesis be considered a holistic legal framework owing to its inability to address the gray areas of this thesis especially the gap in knowledge which is the 'status of refugees' in Nigeria. For not providing any such status it is considered as deficient in scope which makes this most desirable.

⁹³Boring (n.211).

⁹⁴NCFR Act 2004, S 3(1).

⁹⁵Ibid S 20 (1).

⁹⁶ NCFR Act 2004, S 20(2) of and OAU Convention Art. 5(c).

Unlike Nigeria, the constitution of France specially provides legal status for refugees and those seeking asylum generally in France. This is provided under the Asylum and Immigration Law of France. Under this law there are generally two types of asylum protections that are classified by the French asylum law: Refugee status and Subsidiary status. The Refugee status formally would be given to persons satisfying conditions which are defined by Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees of UNHCR. Meanwhile, the subsidiary status could be possibly given to any other type of asylum seekers who do not meet the criteria of refugee status recognition. Generally, one can be given a subsidiary status as long as he/she proves risks of a threat or serious harm to their personal safety once they return to their origin country.⁹⁷ Besides, any of the following situations mentioned by the asylum law could lead to the denial of applications:

- (a) An overt threat could be seen and proven if the applicant wishes to enter French territory;
- (b) A previous sentence or punishment for terrorism had been imposed on the applicant, which would be regarded as a serious harm to the French society.⁹⁸

Other than the legal residency in France, asylum seekers could also apply for French Citizenship as other immigrants. Usually, a five-year of dwelling in France territory would be required before the application, for asylum seekers who get a refugee status, that period could be exempted and they could apply for the naturalisation at once if they wish. However, asylum seekers who get a subsidiary status must still obey the normal rule and no exemptions applied.⁹⁹

Support on personal finance and housing would also become available since the asylum seeker starts his or her application procedure. Normally, if the asylum seeker found himself Under a specific level which is observed by the government, a minimum financial assistance equals to €6.80 per day would be given to the asylum seeker at the end of the month (Lump sum).¹⁰⁰ The number of money support could be changed according to different family populations of asylum seekers. On housing, asylum seekers could temporarily live in the rooms provided by CADA (Centres for the Reception of Asylum Seekers), which could last for six months before the asylum seeker finished finding his or her own place to live.¹⁰¹

Given the above it can validly be said that unlike the Nigerian counterpart the constitution of France entrenched special status and recognition to individuals and persons seeking asylum or refugee status to them. These provisions are wholly lacking under the Nigeria law thereby making the France jurisprudence to be encompassing in this field when placed side by side with its Nigerian counterpart.

7.0 Lesson for Nigeria

Given the above, what is obvious is the fact that Nigeria has a lot of lessons to learn from her counterpart France. Some of these lessons included but not limited to the fact that Nigeria, has to urgently make laws recognizing refugees and as well as providing a special status for them. This status should necessarily include all those recognised as internally displaced persons, asylum seekers, and so on and so forth.

Furthermore, like France Nigeria should establish at least two classes or types of asylum seekers or refugees for protection with various requirements relative to their status. This could be Refugee status and Subsidiary status. The Refugee status formally would be given to persons satisfying conditions which are defined by Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees of UNHCR. Meanwhile, the subsidiary status could be possibly given to any other type of asylum seekers who do not meet the criteria of refugee status recognition. Generally, one can be given a subsidiary status as long as he/she proves risks of a threat or serious harm to their personal safety once they return to their origin country.¹⁰²

⁹⁷Refugees, United Nations High Commissioner for. *"Refugee status, subsidiary protection, and the right to be granted asylum under EC law, Maria-Teresa Gil-Bazo"*UNHCR.

<<https://www.unhcr.org/search/working/45993882/>> Accessed 19th May 2019.

⁹⁸N Boring, *"Refugee Law and Policy: France"*. <<https://www.loc.gov/law/help/refugee-law/france.hph>> Accessed 18th May, 2018

⁹⁹Ibid.

¹⁰⁰Ibid.

¹⁰¹Boring (n.211).

¹⁰²Refugees, United Nations High Commissioner for. *"Refugee status, subsidiary protection, and the right to be granted asylum under EC law, Maria-Teresa Gil-Bazo"*UNHCR.

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Besides, any of the following situations mentioned by the asylum law could lead to the denial of applications:

- (a) An overt threat could be seen and proven if the applicant wishes to enter French territory;
- (b) A previous sentence or punishment for terrorism had been imposed on the applicant, which would be regarded as a serious harm to the French society.¹⁰³

Other than the legal residency in France, asylum seekers could also apply for French Citizenship as other immigrants and Nigeria can also emulate this provision to enhance our laws in this area. Usually, a five-year of dwelling in France territory would be required before the application, for asylum seekers who get a refugee status, that period could be exempted and they could apply for the naturalisation at once if they wish. However, asylum seekers who get subsidiary status must still obey the normal rule and no exemptions applied.¹⁰⁴ This could also be borrowed to enhance Nigerian laws in this area.

As in the case of France, Nigeria could indeed make arrangements to provide some form of support on personal finance and housing to refugees and asylum seekers pending when he or she starts his or her application procedure. Irrespective of the situation asylum and or refugees should at least be provided with some minimum financial assistance to enable them a dissent life.¹⁰⁵ The amount of monetary support could vary according to different family populations of asylum seekers and refugees. Also, housing or shelter could be provided for this group of people to at least enable them to temporarily live a dignified life.¹⁰⁶

8.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

Refugees IDPs in Nigeria lack any status under the Nigerian law. This lack of status has deprived them of basic humanitarian needs, such as the basic necessities of life, especially food, shelter, protection, governmental responsibility and even loss of dignity. The 'status' referred to in this article is a basic condition of living recognised by law for persons displaced by a number of factors including humanitarian, environmental, economic and even political crises. This article therefore makes a case for the protection and security of refugees and other internally displaced persons in Nigeria. Nigeria and perhaps many African countries have a lot to learn from the position in French. Especially, the legal and institutional bodies put in place to be responsible for refugees.

Recommendations

In view of the above it is recommended thus:

- i. That the Nigerian law effectively makes provisions to provide for a special status for refugees in Nigeria as is the case of France which will include internally displaced persons, asylum seekers, and victims of armed violence in Nigeria and elsewhere who seek to gain refuge in Nigeria.
- ii. It is further recommended that Nigeria should establish at least two classes or types of asylum seekers or refugees for protection with various requirements relative to their status. This could be Refugee status and Subsidiary status. The Refugee status formally would be given to persons satisfying conditions which are defined by Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees of UNHCR. Meanwhile, the subsidiary status could be possibly given to any other type of asylum seekers who do not meet the criteria of refugee status recognition. Generally, one can be given a subsidiary status as long as he/she proves risks of a threat or serious harm to their personal safety once they return to their origin country. In granting this 'status' the agencies or bodies responsible should ensure that the persons being granted the said status do not in any pose any form of (a) threat to the corporate existence of Nigeria.

¹⁰³N Boring, "*Refugee Law and Policy: France*". <<https://www.loc.gov/law/help/refugee-law/france.hph>> Accessed 18th May, 2018

¹⁰⁴*Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵*Ibid.*

¹⁰⁶Boring (n.211).

- iii. Other than the legal residency as is the case of France, it is recommended that asylum seekers be allowed to apply for Nigerian Citizenship as other immigrants. The Nigeria law could also make provision to enhance this practice. In this regard, it is further recommended that a five-year of dwelling in France territory would be required before the application, for asylum seekers who get a refugee status, that period could be exempted and they could apply for the naturalisation at once if they wish. However, asylum seekers who get subsidiary status must still obey the normal rule and no exemptions applied. This could also be borrowed to enhance Nigerian laws in this area.
- iv. In line with the position in France, it is recommended that Nigeria could indeed make arrangements to provide some form of support on personal finance and housing to refugees and asylum seekers pending when they commence their application process or procedure. Irrespective of the situation, asylum and or refugees should at least be provided with some minimum financial assistance to enable them to live a decent life. The amount of monetary support could vary according to the different family population of asylum seekers and refugees. Also, housing or helter could be provided for this group of people to at least enable them to temporarily live a dignified life.